

Living in an Impressionist World

Human Experience of Places

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Abstract: Human emotional experience of the physical environment is shaped by five factors. These factors are fundamental, universal sensory processing; individual place experience/history; individual personality; group culture; and national culture. The integration of information gleaned using these five separate factors coalesces perceptions received from the physical environment into individuated emotional experiences. Each of us “feels” uniquely interpreted environments, such as those in impressionist paintings. Universal sensory processing and the cultural factors do, however, provide for some consistent experience of space at the group level. The operation of these place-experience factors leads our place experiences to evolve over time through the modification of memes and, separately, supports the creation and maintenance of positive places. A review of research related to physical environments in which people are creative indicates that the named factors do structure humans’ emotional interaction with their physical environments.

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1. We Are All Impressionists

Although impressionist artists are recognized for registering moods and their reactions to places/situations at a particular moment in time [1], all human beings are in fact impressionists. Each of us uses information-filtering factors/systems to reduce the sensory inputs received from the physical environment to reasonable processing levels and then to interpret and use the information that is ultimately perceived. Just as each impressionist artist has an individual and continually developing painting style, each of us has an environmental interpretation “style“ that is personally contextualized and evolves as our individual experiences accumulate and as group level experiences of place and their cultural underpinnings change.

The physical environment influences the mood of the people experiencing it, through a variety of channels [2]. The five factors that link human exposure to an environment and our completed emotional response to a place each in some way adds subjectivity to assessments, distorting perceptions and informing action. These factors/systems have a rich social component. They ordain that a significant amount of our experience of the physical world is loosely based on physical

experience, and tightly related to the mental interpretation of social information [3]. As Relph relates, “People are their place and the place is the people, and however readily these may be separated in conceptual terms, in experience they are not easily differentiated” [4].

The model of place-experience presented here recognizes five factors that influence human emotional interaction with place. First, humans have a set of fundamental, universal responses to environmental stimuli. These include reactions to color saturation and brightness [5], biophilic design attributes [6], and sound timbre and cadence [7], for example. Second, all human beings have idiosyncratic, place-based experiences/histories which influence how they respond to places they encounter. They involve affective response to particular design elements specifically as well as interpretations of place-based experiences and design elements communicating nonverbally. They can be differentiated from fundamental spaces assessments by their foundation in unique, emotionally charged experiences. Third, individual personality has a decided influence on our emotional response to space. The sort of coordinating psychological response provided at an individual level by personality is delivered at a group level by culture. Groups develop shared responses to life experiences, and those shared concepts influence the ways in which spaces are perceived and used. At both a micro and macro level, cultures influence our relationship to space. The fourth and fifth factors determining emotional response to place are group/organizational and national culture, respectively. Each of these factors exists for purposes in addition to influencing human emotional experience of place.

2. Fundamental, Universal Place Responses

There is a core set of fundamental human emotion-related responses to the physical world. Working with diverse study populations across extended research careers, both Nasar [8] and Steven and Rachel Kaplan [9], for example, have investigated these concepts. Nasar has probed universal human emotional responses to environmental complexity, legibility, mystery, and coherence and Kaplan, Kaplan, and Ryan have studied similar issues as well as access to nature and natural views. Human positive affect increases, for example, in a space that can be understood with minimal effort but is not immediately completely known [10], and when people have access to day light and views of nature [11]. Design elements, such as mobiles overhead and areas with varying ceiling heights and lighting levels (lower and darker opening onto higher and brighter; known as prospect and refuge), mimic comforting attributes of natural spaces and enhance positive affect [12]. These sorts of design elements, which recognize human’s positive emotional response to patterns of experience found in nature, are known as biophilic design [13]. Indoor plants have also been shown to increase positive affect [14].

Human beings respond in a consistent way, across time and culture, to specific sensory situations, such as to the saturation and brightness of colors [5], the forms of shapes [15], and invasions of personal spaces and territories; although in the case of invasions of personal spaces and territories some specifics, such as personal space size, vary by group and national culture [16]. People experience positive affect when they feel that they have control over their physical environments [17] and access to themselves (privacy, [18]). Also, no matter what our cultural background, since our heart starts to

beat in time to music that we hear, music that is slower than our heartbeat (50/70 beats per minute) is calming and music that is faster than that is energizing [7]. We universally find particular sorts of tones pleasing and displeasing. For example, Leeds has shown that we have positive responses to mid-range sounds, such as guitar or chamber instruments, while our responses to higher pitched noises are less positive [7].

Generalized negative responses to stimuli have been researched just as positive responses have been [19]. This paper focuses on positive environmental responses, to illustrate important concepts relevant to the design of places in which people are more likely to be creative (see following focused discussion section), but a corresponding paper could describe attributes of places that consistently encourage negative reactions among human beings. It is not possible to assume that places which engender positive affect have opposite values on key criteria from places that are most likely to lead to negative emotional responses. Rodermann has found, for example, that very complicated wallpaper patterns create tension, but so can starkly simple ones [20].

Being in a place that does not meet our physical and psychological needs results in psychological stress [21]. This psychological stress distracts us from the physical and psychological tasks at hand [22]. Using the model of place experience developed by Russell and Mehrabian [23], it is possible to describe the resulting stress as an aroused, negative state, which can be contrasted with an unaroused negative state (boredom), an unaroused positive state (relaxed), and an aroused positive state (excited). Stress can be created by fundamentally irritating stimuli, such as loud erratic noises, or be more context specific, such as a low mumble of co-worker voices that impedes concentration on a knowledge-intensive task. In these cases the co-worker noise pushes employees into negative affect through its influence on the total stimulation being experienced relative to the optimal stimulation level [24].

3. Individuating Place Experiences

Our individual experiences combine to influence our interpretations of the physical world [25-28] and are uniquely integrated to create customized emotional responses to it. These “impressions” not only vary at any one moment between individual, but also over time for any one person, as that person has place-related experiences that influence perceived nonverbal messages broadcast by particular objects, etc. These variations require that the event be used to organize emotional response to place.

Each of us develops our own dictionary to interpret the symbolic messages sent by the environments and objects in the world around us [29], just as sets of our sensory experiences acquire unshakable positive or negative emotional implications because they are linked to valenced life events [28]. There are generalized socialized associations to design elements, as well [25]. Human sensory apparatus is also variable, affecting information that can possibly be attended (e.g., color blindness).

4. Personality and Place

Multiple aspects of personality have been found to relate to place experience and personality acts as a filter determining if a space or object engenders positive or negative affect [30]. For example, extraverts experience positive affect in spaces that are sensorially rich; these same spaces engender negative affect among introverts [31]. Just as extraverts use the spaces at their disposal to increase their stimulation from inanimate objects, they will also increase the stimulation they receive from other people whenever possible, preferring to stand closer to them than introverts do [32] and to interact with others without intervening barriers, such as table surfaces or chair arms [30].

People with an external locus of control have been found to respond differently to shapes than those with an internal locus control. People in the first group experience more positive affect when viewing curved design elements, while people in the second group have a similar response to rectilinear elements [33]. People with an internal locus of control not only feel in control of their own life, but also the spaces in their lives, and will modify them more readily than people with an external locus of control [30].

People also differ in their personality-based needs for privacy [34], territory [35], sensation [30], and uniqueness [36], each of which has predictable implications for interactions with the surrounding world. People with a higher need for privacy feel a greater level of positive affect when they have it [34], just as people with high territorial needs do in a demarcated personal territory [35]. People who are high in sensation seeking desire more novel or unpredictable places than those who score lower on these personality scales [30]. A higher need for uniqueness can be linked to higher levels of psychological comfort and positive affect in spaces with a greater number of unusual design elements [36].

5. Cultural Responses to Environmental Stimuli

Just as people have idiosyncratic experiences that determine their responses to aspects of their physical environment, they have group-based experiences that influence emotional responses to aspects of places [40]. Amos Rapoport has comprehensively catalogued the link between culturally appropriate space design and positive emotional response [41]. Organizational/group culture and national culture are the fourth and fifth factors, respectively, that influence emotional experience of place. Culture is the collection of values, symbols, behaviors, and rituals shared by a group of people [37]. Every person is a member of a unique set of several different cultures. Cultural groups can be defined in a number of ways, for example: national, vocational, employer, religious, regional, and hobby [38]. The place-based principles of cultures are only fully internalized by the members of those cultures.

National culture has extensive influence on the experience of place. Nisbett and his colleagues [39] have identified society-wide differences in the place experiences of different national cultures - Westerners mainly attend to focal elements while Easterners favor a more holistic, comprehensive review of an image/environment. These differences have a direct implication for the emotional

experience of place. National cultures have different preferred mood states, so the desired emotional effects of various design projects in different cultures are constrained [39]

National culture is a broader organizing concept than group or organizational culture. Gert Hofstede presents a model of national culture that has clear implications for emotional response to place and space design [44]. For example, some cultures value individual independence more than social interdependence and in other cultures the situation is reversed. People living in an independence-prizing culture have positive psychological experiences when they can represent their own individual identity in a space, while members of cultures that respect interdependence have the opposite response and wish to express group identity via space design. People from independence-valuing cultures also expect to spend more time alone than people who live in more interdependent cultures, which means that they are more apt to experience negative affect and stress when sharing spaces. People in independence-focused cultures are also more apt to modify spaces to meet their psychological needs, and are thus more likely to experience stress when they cannot do so than people living in a collectivist culture. Zimring and Peatross carefully investigated the relationship between national culture and space design, finding relationships between national culture, place form, and affective response [45]. Edgar Schein, in his discussions of physical environments that support organizational/group culture, has clearly illustrated the emotional importance of linking place design with group level culture [37]. When culture is supported by place and place by culture, functional harmony consistent with positive affect results.

People choose to surround themselves with objects and design elements that are consistent with the positive aspects of their self-concept, and the meaning systems linking particular objects or design elements to positive or negative responses have a cultural component [42], just as they have an individualized one. Prized personalizing objects are associated with positive emotional consequences. When the meaning tied to an associated object or place (either purchased or assigned), is inconsistent with the self-concept of the owner, particularly strong and negative responses can ensue [43].

Culture is not static. Memetic evolution leads cultural evolution. Memes are mental representation of cultural values, rules, and memories [46] and are learned through socialization [47]. Built environments and objects facilitate this education [48]. Although memes exist at a cultural level, people have personalized copies of memes [49]. Over time, experiences change those individual memes, and, if changes made have biological or cultural advantages, individual meme changes become integrated into society-wide memes [50, 49]. Sustainable architecture has significant differences from architectural forms that were previously present in the developed world, but the evolution of place-based memes is beginning to form more positive emotional responses to elements of the sustainable built environment [51], for example. Individual level meme changes influence more immediate group collective memes before they influence memes of more loosely associated groups.

6. Pertinence of Place-Based Affective Response

Space design has a significant influence on human well-being, through its ability to affect us emotionally [52]. Positive affect is usually defined as “pleasant feelings induced by commonplace events or circumstances” [53, page 1] and the definition for negative affect is generally the reverse [54]. Positive affect has been linked to broadened thinking/attention and thought-action repertoires, when compared to neutral or negative state processing [55]. In general, positive affect has been positively related to: improved creative performance and increased innovation [56]; improved problem solving and decision making [57]; more flexible, thorough, and efficient thinking on topics meaningful or interesting to the thinker [57]; strategic thinking [58]; constructive and cooperative bargaining, increased generosity, social responsibility, helping and interpersonal understanding [57]; constructive suggestions [59]; avoidance of real and meaningful risk [56]; and improved self-knowledge [60]. Positive emotions can help build durable personal resources such as physical skills or health, social resources such as friendships and networks, intellectual resources such as knowledge, and psychological resources such as optimism [55].

Negative affect also clearly relates to specific behaviors. In addition to not exhibiting the linkages noted above for positive affect, it encourages thorough, analytical, detail-oriented, systematic thinking, but in more focused areas and narrower thought-action repertoires than in a neutral state [61, 55]. Brief and Weiss report that negative affect in the workplace has been associated with negative interpersonal interactions, anxiety, more extreme emotions after negative work experiences, and reduced positive response to desirable workplace events [62]. Negative affect and positive affect are not necessarily related to inverse patterns of mental processing, behaviors, etc. [63].

Individuals intuitively understand the sorts of spaces that will optimize their place-based experiences [28]. They can individually perform the complicated mental gymnastics required to conceptualize the appropriate space design for a person with their personality, working within their national and organizational culture, etc. While they understand at a pre-verbal level the design of an appropriate space, they often do not have the vocabulary to discuss the appropriate design criteria [64]. They know the feelings that they should have in an optimally designed space, and can recognize those feelings when they are presented to them in images [65].

7. Designing for Creativity – Emotional Design Focused Discussion

Place-designers are regularly asked to design spaces in which people are more likely to be creative and also are encouraged to work creatively to resolve space-design issues. The five place-experience factors are pertinent to the design of spaces that support creativity - using the physical environment to induce positive affect seems particularly desirable when spaces for creativity are being developed. We will focus on group spaces that sustain creative thoughts and action. As the following paragraphs will illustrate, a body of evidence is building about the physical design of places in which people are likely to be most creative. They are indeed spaces that put people in a good mood.

Although a number of definitions of creativity are possible [66], we will define creativity as Sternberg has, to refer to the production of high quality novel ideas that are related to resolution of the focal issue [67]. Hennessey and Amabile, in a recent literature review, indicate that creative performance is related not only to individual level constructs such as neurology, mood, and personality, but also to the social environment and culture. After reviewing a complex body of research they conclude that “positive affect is more conducive to creativity than negative affect” [68, page 575], because creative performance more generally requires broad thinking than narrow, more constrained analyses. Creativity researchers on occasion recognize that creative behavior occurs in a physical, temporal and social environment, and that physical space can influence creative performance [69, 70], but attention to time and place is far from universal. Even when “places for creativity” are discussed by researchers, aspects of the environments that would allow conclusions to be drawn about the moods induced by the physical environments are rarely presented.

McCoy and Evans [71] conducted one of the first rigorous studies of the influence of the physical environment on creative performance. Their findings indicate that aspects of the physical environment that increase positive affect are associated with creative performance, and that the five place-experience factors noted above are pertinent to the design of spaces to facilitate creative behavior. For example, they determined that views of the natural environment are associated with higher levels of creative performance as is moderate visual complexity, just as the place-experience factors would suggest. In addition, they learned that use of natural materials is higher in spaces in which people perceive they are more likely to be creative. Their research findings that spaces in which people perceive as supporting creativity are more likely to use fewer cool colors are difficult to assess because the saturation and brightness levels of the colors used in this study are not provided.

A direct assessment of the influence of the physical environment on mood and creativity was conducted by Ceylan, Dul, and Aytac [72]. Their findings are consistent with those that would be expected based on the place-experience factors described. They determined that perceptions of creativity performance are higher for places that have views of nature, more indoor plants, moderate visual complexity, appropriate work tools, and bright (but comfortable) lighting levels. All of these conditions would be predicted a priori to induce positive affect. Analyses of color related findings and their influence on emotional experience from this study are difficult to assess because color saturation and brightness are not described.

Csikszentmihalyi discusses physical environments and creativity extensively [73]. He states that the form of the physical environment should be different at various stages of the creative process to support pivotal activities. During data gathering phases, which researchers besides Csikszentmihalyi might define as a “pre-creative” period, he encourages use of an environment that application of the five place-experience factors indicates is emotionally neutral, while during phases requiring broad thinking, Csikszentmihalyi suggests the use of places that broaden thinking and that analysis shows increase positive affect. These creativity facilitating spaces have expansive views of nature, for

example. Csikszentmihalyi also indicates that spaces that support creativity are task appropriate (allow concentration), reflect user personality and work style, and are personalized in user-meaningful ways.

Describing physical office space at the design firm IDEO that supports creative performance, Tim Brown, the current chief executive officer at the firm, presents spaces that the place-related research described earlier would associate with positive affect [74]. For example, workers have a great deal of personal control over the form of their workplaces at IDEO and are able to change them easily. Spaces are equipped with tools consistent with the required tasks. Brown's comments about spaces in which people are creative are consistent with the creative spaces described by IDEO's founder, Tom Kelly [75]. In the spaces Kelly describes, workers are able to extensively personalize their workstations and have ready access to needed resources, including the opportunity to interact with others or isolate themselves to concentrate, as needed. National and organizational culture based needs and nonverbal communication are respected and reflected in those creative work environments and spaces are infused with daylight. Innovation centers clearly and often nonverbally communicate to users the value the sponsoring organizations place on workers and their ability to innovate [76, 77]. This nonverbal encouragement is consistent with increases in positive affect.

Additional studies of spaces and creativity have indicated instances in which the physical environment has reduced creativity by engendering negative affect. For example, irritating and uncontrollable noises and lack of appropriate privacy have this effect [78].

8. Conclusions

Five place-experience factors have a significant influence on the ways in which we perceive and use environments and coordinate emotional experience of place. They include fundamental/universal sensory processing, individual place experience, individual personality, and group/organizational and national cultures. They guide the creation and maintenance of positive places. A review of research related to physical environments in which people are creative indicates that the place-experience system described does structure people's emotional interaction with their physical environments.

9. References

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